

A Study of Surgical Outcomes of Tympanoplasties with and Without Cortical Mastoidectomy

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Abstract:

Background: Tympanoplasty, or eardrum repair, is a surgical procedure used to fix a ruptured tympanic membrane (eardrum) or the small bones of the middle ear. An eardrum perforation may result from chronic infections or, less commonly, eardrum trauma.

Objective: The study's goal is to compare the surgical results of mastoidectomies and tympanoplasties in terms of improved hearing and graft uptake.

Methods: This Prospective study conducted at tertiary care hospital of Middle Gujarat, India and a total of 60 patients undergoing tympanoplasties with and without mastoidectomy were included and followed up for a period of one year.

Results: The surgical results of the two procedures did not differ significantly in terms of improved hearing or graft uptake. When applied unilaterally, the Belfast rule of thumb allows the patient to truly benefit from their hearing.

Conclusion: CSOM seems to be more prevalent among females. The enhancement in hearing after undergoing either tympanoplasty alone or combined tympanoplasty with mastoidectomy demonstrated similar outcomes in both cohorts. It was observed that incorporating mastoidectomy into tympanoplasty did not yield additional advantages in terms of improvement in hearing.

Keywords: cortical Mastoidectomy, Tympanoplasty, Belfast rule.

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Introduction

Chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM) is characterized as a persistent and gradually developing condition, often leading to significant damage to middle ear structures. Clinically, it presents with some symptoms such as deafness and discharge persisting for over three months. This condition, prevalent since ancient times, remains a significant contributor to the middle ear ailments and stands as one of the most prevalent ear disorders in developing nations. [1] The ratio of disease prevalence between urban and rural areas is 1:2, with the highest occurrence observed in economically disadvantaged rural communities. [2,3]

The incidence of chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM) is heightened among individuals with lower socioeconomic status, suboptimal nutritional conditions, and insufficient health education, with a

particular prevalence observed in rural populations. [4] Tympanoplasty, also called eardrum repair, refers to surgery performed to reconstruct a perforated tympanic membrane (eardrum) or the small bones of the middle ear. Eardrum perforation may result from chronic infection or, less commonly, from trauma to the eardrum.

Repairing the ruptured eardrum and occasionally the middle ear bones, which include the incus, malleus, and stapes, is the goal of tympanoplasty. Grafting of the tympanic membrane can be necessary. Grafts from a vein or fascia (muscle sheath) tissue on the ear lobe are typically used when necessary. [5,6] Patients who have had prior surgeries and have restricted access to grafts may be treated with synthetic materials. Directly below the ear and attached to the middle ear area is the mastoid, a

honeycomb cavity in the temporal bone. Mastoid surgery is frequently required to relieve eardrum holes caused by prior trauma or infection, or when a chronic infection with middle ear or mastoid tissue continues. This part of the procedure is called mastoidectomy. Surgery for tubotympanic type of chronic suppurative otitis media is the commonest otological surgical procedure in our country [7]

This study examines the several pre-operative variables that significantly impact the outcome of two different surgeries: cortical mastoidectomy with type 1 tympanoplasty and myringoplasty. The closing of the air bone gap determines the hearing benefit, and the Belfast rule of thumb is used to subjectively assess hearing.

Materials and Methods

This Prospective study was conducted at ENT Department of Parul Sevashram hospital, Vadodara, Gujarat from July 2022 to Aug 2024.

Study Involves total 60 patients attending ENT OPD with mucosal disease at Our hospital for a period of one year and the patients were followed up for a period of one year.

Inclusion criteria: After localised sepsis has been ruled out, patients of both sexes aged 15 to 50 with wet or dry ears and pure tone audiometry demonstrating conductive hearing loss.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients with congenital or acquired abnormalities of ear, unsafe ear, and undergone ear surgeries previously and with pure tone audiometry showing mixed and sensorineural hearing loss were excluded from the study.

Methodology: Minimum duration of discharge for the patients under study was 1 year and maximum was 15 years. Minimum duration of hearing impairment was 6 months and maximum was 10 years. For all patients, under study with wet ears, ear swabs were taken from middle ear and for patients with culture positive results, treated with specific antibiotics prior to surgery.

All cases were admitted, pre-operative examination done under microscopy, subjected to endoscopic eustachian tube evaluation (those with normally looking pharyngeal end of eustachian tube orifice were taken up for study) and hearing assessment done with tuning fork tests and pure tone audiogram. All patients were informed about their need for a follow up period of one year. Informed written consent to undergo surgery was obtained from all patients. Mastoid shaving and local preparation was done in the ward prior to surgery. All cases were done under GA. Premedication and local infiltration was same for all cases.

Group A: About 30 patients with dry ear for more than 6 weeks and with only conductive hearing loss, were subjected to myringoplasty and

considered as Group A. About 16 patients with unilateral disease and 14 patients with bilateral disease were taken up for study. For patients with bilateral disease, worse ear was taken up for surgery. All patients were taken up for surgery under GA. Trans canal approach was followed in 25 cases and in 5 cases with narrow external auditory canal post-aural approach was followed. 4 quadrant local infiltration was given with 2% xylocaine with adrenaline premixed solution. Temporalis fascia graft harvested by a separate incision over supra auricular region for patients done through trans-canal approach & in patients done through post-aural approach, graft was harvested via the same incision. Temporalis fascia graft kept by underlay technique. All cases were followed up for 3,6 months and one year for graft uptake and postoperative hearing evaluations done at 3,6 months and one year. Results of hearing benefit, compared with pre-op and post-op air bone gap and for unilateral disease Belfast rule of thumb applied.

Group B: About 30 patients with wet ear and with no active infection as per microbiological report & with conductive hearing loss were subjected to cortical mastoidectomy with type 1 tympanoplasty and considered as Group B.

About 20 patients with unilateral disease and 10 patients with bilateral disease were taken up for study. For patients with bilateral disease, worse ear was taken up for surgery. All patients were taken up for surgery under GA. Post-aural approach was followed in all cases. Post aural incision made, temporalis fascia graft harvested through the superior aspect of the incision as the first step, incision deepened and mastoid cortex exposed. Pinna retracted anteriorly, incision made in the posterior canal wall skin from 6 o'clock to 12 o'clock position and tympanomeatal flap was elevated. Granulations if present in the tympanum were removed, mobility of ossicular chain were checked. Mastoid cortex was drilled out in all cases, patency established. For about 21 patients granulations noted in antrum removed and in 4 patients antrum found free of disease. For all patients, temporalis fascia graft kept by underlay technique, tympanomeatal flap repositioned and post-aural wound closed in layers. All cases were followed up for 2, 6 months and 1 year for graft uptake and post-operative hearing evaluations done at 3, 6 months and 1 year. Results of hearing benefit, compared with pre-op and post-op air bone gap and for unilateral disease, Belfast rule of thumb applied.

Results

Total number of cases registered in this study was 60 patients, who came to the ENT Department with Mucosal disease.

The overall graft take up rate in both the surgeries was 88.33%. The overall hearing benefit was 90%, excellent with < 10dB ABG in 51.67% and Good with < 20dB in 38.33%. There was no postoperative complications, deterioration in hearing or sensorineural hearing loss in all 60 patients.

In Group A, 20 were females & 10 were males, 16 patients had unilateral and 14 had bilateral disease, 20 had medium sized central perforation and 10 had subtotal perforation, 15 had good pre-op Air bone gap of 10 to 20 dBHL 15 patients had a fair pre-op Air bone gap of 20 to 30 dBHL.

1. Overall graft take up rate was 86.6%.
2. Otoscopic evaluation of 20 patients with medium sized perforation at the end of 2 months, revealed 15 to be intact, 5 residual perforation in the antero - inferior quadrant. In 5 patients with subtotal perforation, 3 were intact, 1 with residual perforation & 1 grafts got rejected because of post-op wound infection. Otoscopic examination at the end of 6 months & 1 year revealed – for all 20 patients with medium size perforation, tympanic membrane was intact and out of 5 patients with subtotal 2 were with residual perforation & 1 with rejection of graft. Hence the size of the perforation does have a role in graft take up rate. This is statistically significant by applying chi square test with p value < 0.05.
3. In 15 patients with good pre-op ABG, the post-op ABG was excellent. In 15 patients with fair pre-op ABG, the post-op ABG results were, excellent in 9, good in 8 and fair in 3 patients accounting for 46.66% in excellent, 40% in good and 13% in fair groups. By applying Chi square test, these results are statistically significant. Hence, for the patients with lesser pre-operative Air bone gap have a better post-operative hearing.
4. When Belfast rule of thumb was applied to 16 patients with unilateral disease, 10 of them with medium sized perforation, felt subjectively better and out of 3 of them with subtotal perforation, 2 felt better & 1 patient felt hearing same as the pre-operative status. These results are statistically significant with p value < 0.05, implies that Belfast rule of thumb interpret the post-operative hearing benefit in a better way than the Air bone gap, which tells about only the technical success.
5. The correlation coefficient between the duration of discharge and the pre-op ABG is 0.4172 and that between the duration of hearing impairment with pre-op ABG is 0.3821 and is statistically significant. The correlation coefficient between the duration of discharge and the post-op ABG is 0.4544 and that between the duration of hearing impairment with post-op ABG is 0.4489 and is statistically significant, implies that the patients

with lesser duration of discharge and hearing impairment had better post-operative hearing than the patients with longer duration of disease and hearing impairment.

6. The other parameters, such as age, sex, weight does not have influence on the outcome of results in this study.
7. The type of approach does not have a significant p value with graft intake in this study. Applying chi square test, the Pearson value is 0.

In Group B, 22 were females & 8 were males, 20 patients had unilateral and 10 had bilateral disease. 18 had medium central perforation and 12 had subtotal perforation, 08 had good pre-op Air bone gap of 10 to 20 dBHL, 22 patients had a fair pre-op Air bone gap of 20 to 30 dBHL.

1. Overall graft take up rate was 90%.
 2. The relationship between Graft take up rate and size of the perforation is statistically significant by applying chi square test with person value of 0.02535.
- Otosopic evaluation of 18 patients with medium sized perforation at the end of 2 months, revealed 16 to be intact, 2 residual perforation in the antero-inferior quadrant. In 12 patients with subtotal perforation, 08 were intact, 4 with residual perforation. Otoscopic examination at the end of 6 months & 1 year revealed – for all 18 patients with medium size perforation, tympanic membrane was intact and out of 12 patients with subtotal 4 were with residual perforation. Hence the size of the perforation do have a role in graft take up rate even when cortical mastoidectomy is done along with repair of tympanic membrane.
3. In this study, out of 18 patients with medium sized perforation, 8 had a good & 22 had fair pre-op ABG. Out of 12 patients with subtotal perforation, 9 patient had well & 03 had fair pre-op ABG, implies that 85.71 % of the patients with subtotal perforation had pre-op ABG of 20 to 30 dB.

4. Out of 30 patients, included in this procedure, 50% had excellent, 50% had well & 10% had fair post-op ABG. Those with medium sized perforation had better results than those with subtotal perforation.
5. On comparison of pre-op ABG & post-op ABG, all 8 patients with good pre-op ABG improved to excellent, out of 22 with fair ABG, 3 were excellent, 16 were good and 3 were fair post-operatively. This result is highly statistically significant with pearson value of 0.00006.
6. Graft intake in 4 patients with disease free antrum mucosa is 100%.

7. Out of 30 patients, 26 patients had disease in the antrum & 4 had a healthy antrum. 77.85% of the patients with healthy antrum and 9.5% of the patients with diseased antrum had good pre-op Air bone gap 90.5% with diseased and 22.2% with healthy antrum had fair preop Air bone gap.

8. In patients with healthy antrum, the post-op ABG was excellent in 88.9% and 66.7% of the patients with diseased antrum had a good ABG post-operatively.

9. On applying Belfast rule of thumb to 10 patients with unilateral disease, 83.3% had better hearing, implies the post-operative hearing benefit better than assessment with Air bone gap.

10. The correlation coefficient between the duration of discharge and the pre-op ABG is 0.3803 and that between the duration of hearing impairment with pre-op ABG is 0.3776.

The correlation coefficient between the duration of discharge and the post-op ABG is 0.3794 and that

between the duration of hearing impairment with pre-op ABG is 0.3729 and are statistically significant, implies that the patients with lesser duration of discharge and hearing impairment had better post-operative hearing than the patients with longer duration of disease and hearing impairment.

11. The other parameters, such as age, sex, weight does not have influence on the outcome of results in this study.

Discussion

Analysis of 60 cases undergone surgery for tubotympanic disease is presented here and the same is compared with similar and related studies available in literature.

1. Graft Take Up Rate:

The overall graft take up rate in Myringoplasty in this study was 86.6%, which is within the range to the studies available. The graft take up rate in various studies were [Table 1];

Table 1: Graft take up rate.[8]

Study	No of cases	year	Graft take up rate
Gibb, Chang et al	365	1982	91.4%
Black, PJ Wormald	261	1995	78%
Raj A Vedit	50	1999	84%
Kotecha et al	107	1999	82.2%
Yasuo, Mishiro et al	104	2001	94.4%
Kageyama et al	290	2001	82.1%
Alberrra et al	85	2006	86%

The graft take up rate in cortical mastoidectomy with type 1 tympanoplasty is 90% which is also within the range to the studies available in literature [Table 2].

Table 2: Graft take up rate.[9]

Studies	No of cases	Graft take up rate
Yasuo, Mishiro et al	147	90%
Adnan saleem et al	85	92.95%
McGrew et al	100	91%
Rehl CM et al	135	90.4%

2. Graft Failure Rate: Graft failure rate in various studies were [Table 3];

Table 3: Re-perforation Rate %.[8]

Studies	Re-perforation Rate %
Alberrra et al	7 to 21
Vartianien et al	10.6
Adnan, saleem et al	7.05

In this study, in myringoplasty series the rate of residual perforation is 6.7% and the rate of rejection of graft is 6.7%.

The probable cause of residual perforation is the slippage of the graft from its position and the cause for rejection is the post-operative infection of the operated site, which is same as the reason cited by the study of Vartianien et al and Kotecha et

al.[10,11] Study of Alberrra et al also includes the efficiency of the surgeon and the surgical techniques.[8]

3. Pre-operative Hearing: In this study the pre-operative pure tone average in Myringoplasty series was between 30 to 40 dB with average being 38 dB and in Cortical mastoidectomy with type 1 tympanoplasty series between 30 to 55 dB with

average being 42.16 dB. As the perforation size increases, the preoperative hearing threshold also increases – this is consistent with the study conducted by Mehta et al, Bhusal et al Nepal A Bhandary et al, Kageyama et al, Aiberra et al and Saeed et al.[8]

4. Post-Operative Hearing Benefit: Hearing improvement in various studies quoted in literature were [Table 4];

Table 4: Hearing Improvement.[8,9]

Study	Hearing Improvement
Adnan et al	85.88%
Rizer et al	84.9%
Raj A Vidit et al	68%
Kotecha et al	67%

In this study, the overall post-operative hearing benefit based on Air bone gap was 90% with <10 Db in 51.67% and <20db in 38.33%. As hearing benefit is better assessed with the subjective evaluation, in this study we have applied Belfast rule of thumb in patients with unilateral disease.

In 23 patients with unilateral disease in Myringoplasty series, 95.7% felt significant improvement in hearing and 4.3% felt no improvement.

In 18 patients with unilateral disease in Mastoidectomy with type 1 tympanoplasty series, 83.3% felt significant improvement in hearing and 16.7% felt no improvement.

Conclusion

From Our study we would like to conclude that the success of Myringoplasty in terms of graft uptake and hearing improvement is better in patients with lesser duration of disease, less preoperative Air bone gap and with medium sized perforations when compared to subtotal perforations. The success of cortical mastoidectomy with type tympanoplasty in terms of graft uptake and hearing improvement is better in patients with lesser duration of disease and less pre-operative Air bone gap.

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